

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PATIENT INFORMEDNESS ON THE REGULATION OF ACCESS TO SOCIALISED OUTPATIENT MEDICAL CARE

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ABSTRACT

The patients' access to medical care is one of the indicators used to assess healthcare systems. After the establishment of the general practitioner institution, the access to specialist outpatient care has been conducted after a specialist referral is secured. The National Health Insurance Fund operates on a fixed budget that's established by law, and there is no funding for payments in case physicians report more physical exams. In case the limit for referrals is reached, any health-insured person may be declined a physical exam and the needed medical care may not be covered by the budget, to which the patient contributes on a regular basis. In relation to this, we conducted a questionnaire-style study among patients, looking into their informedness on the limit for specialist referrals, the date by which the referral can be used, and GP feedback. The results show that 73.1% of the respondents know that specialist referrals have a quantity limit, while 93.1% are aware of the time limit for using specialist referrals issued by the GP. 62.3% inform their general practitioner when they have not used a specialist referral they were issued. Bearing in mind the fact that this system of regulation and time limits has functioned for over 20 years (without having experienced any change to the rules for issuing specialist referrals and their time limits) we can draw a conclusion concerning the patients' lack of responsibility in spending the NHIF's limited resources at the outpatient level.

Keywords: regulation, limit, specialist referrals, GP, access.

Introduction:

According to Bulgarian legislation, it is the right of every Bulgaria citizen to receive medical care, under the terms and procedure established in the Health Act and Health Insurance Act. The terms and procedure for realising the right to access medical care are determined with an ordinance by the Council of Ministers (<https://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2135527794/>).

After the establishment of the general practitioner institution, the access to specialist outpatient care has been conducted after a specialist referral is secured. The access regulation applied is simultaneously the main financial regulatory mechanism in the closed healthcare system implemented in Bulgaria. Most often, closed payment systems for compensating medical service providers are applied in insurance cost containment policies globally and in Europe. On the other hand, the policy of cost-sharing among the insured is expanding, resulting in more citizens and patients contributing to payments and consumer charges at the time of the service (Yanev G., 2000).

ANALYSIS

The goal of our study is to analyse some aspects of access to specialists in outpatient medical care.

To realise this goal the following tasks were assigned:

1. An analysis of the frequency and number of specialist referrals issued by GPs.
2. Patient informedness on the limit to the quantity of specialist referrals and the time limits for their use.
3. An analysis of the frequency of use for specialist referrals.
4. An analysis of the patient's feedback to their GP.

The study is a part of a larger questionnaire-based research related to specialised outpatient care. It was conducted in the 18.04.2023 - 31.07.2023 period through the Google Forms online platform. 509 patients from all over the country responded. 63.3% of them were women and 36.7% were men. The largest proportion of respondents fell in the 31-40 age range - 31.6%, followed by the 41-50 age group - 24.2%, and the over 60 age group -22.6%. The under 30 age group was had the smallest number - 7.3%.

The questions regarding the respondents' social status shows that more than 3/4 (76%) of them are employed, followed by those who are unemployed - 9.8%, the students (5.8%) and the retirees - 5.7 %.

We asked the respondents whether they receive specialist referrals from their GP if they express interest in one. The results are presented on Figure 1.

Figure 1. Do you receive specialist referral from your GP if request it

More than half of the respondents (60.9%) reported experiencing no issues with obtaining a specialist referral and always receive one from their GP, and 9.2% reported receiving a specialist referral at the beginning of the calendar month. This result is legitimate, as GPs have a limit on referrals for specialist physician consultations and exceeding it can lead to the corresponding penalties. Over a quarter (26.5%) only receive specialist referrals sometimes, while only 1% answer in the negative. Only 2.4% couldn't give a definite answer.

We asked the participants how many specialist referrals they obtain from their GP for a year (Figure 2). The results show that most of the respondents receive 2 referrals per year from GPs (29, 86%), followed by those who report that they receive one specialist referral per year (18.47%) and those who report receiving three referrals (18,27%). Nearly ¼ (18,27%) report receiving between 4 and 10 referrals per year from their GP, and 8.64% receive referrals whenever needed. As little as 5.11% answer that they receive referrals very rarely or that they do not use specialist referrals from a GP.

Figure 2. Number of specialist referrals received from GPs for one year

We asked several questions to assess whether patients were aware of the existence of limits on specialist referrals and the time limits for their use.

We asked "Are you aware that there is a limit to the number of specialist referrals?". A positive response

was given by 73.1% of respondents, while over ¼ (26.9%) were ignorant of the existence of this regulation (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Respondents' informedness on the existence of a limit on specialist referrals

The next question relates to whether patients know that they must use the specialist referral they have obtained within 30 days of its being issued. Only 6.9%

gave a negative response, while 93.1% were aware of the time limits for using specialist referrals issued by GPs (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Respondents' informedness on the time limits for using a specialist referral (within 30 days after its being issued)

We asked the questionnaire respondents if they always used the specialist referral they received from their GP (Figure 5). The purpose of this question is to assess the patients' responsibility and efficiency in using the NHIF's limited resources. The results showed

that 88.6% of the respondents used their specialist referrals, while 6.9% said they used referrals if they found time, and 4.6% gave a negative response. That is, 11.5% of all respondents did not take a responsible approach to efficiently use the NHIF's limited resources.

Figure 5. Do you always use your specialist referrals.

We looked for a relationship between the utilisation of specialist referrals obtained from GPs and the respondents' place of residence (Table 1). The results show that the largest portion (68.1%) of the respondents residing in the capital city (Sofia) always use the

specialist referrals they obtain from their GPs (they respond with a definitive "yes"). The most likely reason for this is the more abundant availability of specialist physicians and the quicker access through the NHIF.

Table 1.

Relationship between the utilisation of specialist referrals and place of residence

Place of residence	town		province center city		village		the capital (Sofia)	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Yes	47	47.0%	11	30.6%	21	51.2%	226	68.1%
Mostly yes	33	33.0%	16	44.4%	18	43.9%	79	23.8%
No	1	1.0%	0	0.0%	1	2.4%	7	2.1%
Mostly no	4	4.0%	0	0.0%	1	2.4%	9	2.7%
If I find the time	15	15.0%	9	25.0%	0	0.0%	11	3.3%

We asked the respondents if they informed their GP if they did not use a specialist referral in order to assess patient responsibility. The results showed that 62.3% informed their GP when they did not use the specialist referral they had received, while over 1/3 (33.4%) did not inform their GP, and 4.3% reported that

they informed their GP if they found time. These results suggest that it is necessary to work towards increasing patient informedness when it comes to the limits and scarcity of the resources provided through mandatory health insurance in order to increase the efficiency of their use (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Do you inform your GP if you do not use a specialist referral you have received?

CONCLUSION

The reason for these results should be sought, firstly, in the patients - for not being informed on the rules and regulations for using referrals, and, secondly, in the GPs - for not informing the patients on the existing time limits for using specialist referrals. Bearing in mind the fact that this system of regulation and time limits has functioned for over 20 years, without having experienced any change to the rules for issuing specialist referrals and their time limits, we can draw a conclusion concerning the patients' lack of responsibility in spending the NHIF's limited resources at the outpatient level. It is necessary for informational campaigns to be organised, or information brochures to be distributed, with the aim of increasing informedness on patient responsibility.

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